

DETERMINATION OF SALINITY TOLERANCE IN TOMATO CULTIVARS GROWN IN BASRAH, IRAQ

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Abstract:

The development of salt-tolerant tomato genotypes is a basic necessity to defeat the challenges of tomato production under salinity in the field or soil-free farming. Two types of salinity tolerance genes were used SOD and GPX using real time PCR technique under different concentration of NaCl (3, 6 and 9 decimals), for different groups of tomato plants.

Keywords: Solanum Spp.; SOD; GPX ; tomato; salt stress; salt-stress related genes.

Introduction:

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersium* Mill.) is an annual herbaceous plant and a affiliate to the Solanaceae family. Cultivated tomatoes are classified as fairly sensitive to salinity. Mining for salt tolerance possible in tomato wild qualified species started in 1941 by Lyon [1]. The genetic variability for salt tolerance is limited in cultivated tomatoes, while the wild Solanum species have been reported as a foundation of salt tolerance such as Solanum pimpinellifolium, Solanum Pennellii (SP), Solanum cheesmaniae, Solanum habrochaites (*Lycopersicon hirsutum*), Solanum chmielewskii, and Solanum peruvianum [2]. During domestication, abiotic stress tolerance has been lost in cultivated tomatoes.

One of the strategy in a tomato proliferation program that aim to increase tolerance to biotic and abiotic stresses is to use native germplasm or wild relatives for the introgression of new allelic combinations in the current varieties.

In this study, we determine the salt tolerance stage of SOD and GPX genes in. The SOD and GPX gene expression level evaluated using quantification of transcripts accumulation by qRT-PCR. Furthermore, these genes can be used as rootstocks in grafting experiment under saline irrigation situation.

Materials and Methods

Gene Expression

Freshly fruits of tomato plants were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for RNA extraction. Total RNA was extracted using ZR Plant RNA Minipreps™ RNA isolation kit (USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions, and finally, the residual genomic DNA was removed by DNaseI enzyme. First-strand cDNA was synthesized with the PrimeScript™ kit (Takara, USA) using 1 µg of total RNA different biological tomato Plants for each treatment according to the supplier's standard protocol. cDNA was used as a template for

qRT-PCR reactions. Each reaction was performed in 10 μ L its containing illustrate in table 1 (3) . The qPCR reactions were carried out using the following protocol in table 2 (4) .

The two tested salt receptive genes used in qPCR reactions were SOD and GPX , the relative quantification of gene expression was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method [5].

Table 1: qRT-PCR reactions for SOD and GPX genes

Final concentration	Final volume	content
2x	10 μ L	KAPA SYBR FAST qPCR Master Mix (2X) Universal
0.2 μ M	0.4 μ L	Forward primer
0.2 μ M	0.4 μ L	Reverse primer
	Up to 10 μ L	Nuclease-free water
1pg-100ng	-	Template DNA Sample Volume

Table 2: The qPCR protocol SOD and GPX genes

Scanning	Cycle	Time	Temp. ($^{\circ}$ C)	Step
	Hold	05:00 min	95 $^{\circ}$ C	Enzyme activation
	40	:00:20	95.0 $^{\circ}$ C	Denaturation
		:00:20 sec	60.0 $^{\circ}$ C	Annealing
		:00:20 sec	72.0 $^{\circ}$ C	/Extension

Results

The expression profile of salt reactive genes in Tomato SOD and GPX were molecularly selected depending on the previous studies. The expression profiles of two salt tolerance related genes SOD and GPX genes were investigated in the tomato samples in response to 3,6 and 9 decimals NaCl after treatment show in both tables 3 and 4 .

Table 3: the effect of salinity on (SOD)Superoxide dismutase gene expression

Folding SOD	$\Delta\Delta Ct$ SOD	ΔCt SOD	SOD	EF-alpha	Salt concentration decimal	
		8.5	24.1	17.0	1	3
0.615572	0.7	9.2	25.5	16.9	2	
2.639016	-1.4	7.1	25.6	17.2	3	
		8.2	25.3	17.2	4	
1.071773	-0.1	8.1	25.5	17.3	5	
1.624505	-0.7	7.5	25.2	17.6	1	6
		6.7	25.1	18.2	2	
0.757858	0.4	7.1	24.6	17.7	3	

1	0	6.7	25.5	18.0	4	9
		6.6	25.5	18.1	5	
0.466516	1.1	7.7	25.1	17.6	1	
0.574349	0.8	7.4	25.5	17.7	2	
		8.4	25.8	16.9	3	
1	0	8.4	25.7	16.7	4	
1.866066	-0.9	7.5	25.5	17.3	5	

Table 4: the effect of salinity on expression of GPX (Glutathione peroxidase) gene

folding GPX	$\Delta\Delta Ct$ GPX	ΔCt GPX	GPX	EF-alpha	المعاملات التركيز (ديسيمينز)	
		8.5	25.5	17.0	1	3
1	0	8.5	25.4	16.9	2	
1.866066	-0.9	7.6	24.8	17.2	3	
		8.3	25.5	17.2	4	6
0.870551	0.2	8.5	25.8	17.3	5	
1.741101	-0.8	7.5	25.1	17.6	1	
		7.4	25.6	18.2	2	
0.812252	0.3	7.7	25.4	17.7	3	
1.071773	-0.1	7.3	25.3	18.0	4	9
		7.2	25.3	18.1	5	
0.101532	3.3	10.5	28.1	17.6	1	
1.624505	-0.7	6.5	24.2	17.7	2	
		8.4	25.3	16.9	3	
0.659754	0.6	9	25.7	16.7	4	
1.414214	-0.5	7.9	25.2	17.3	5	

The relative expression level of two genes SOD and GPX in tomato plants increased with salt treatment in comparison with that of control plants, which means these genes are involved in plant response to salt tension.

For SOD gene, the cultivar (Koka1) recorded the highest gene expression at the salinity level (3) decimals followed by the genotype (Nawal1) at the salinity level (9) decimal, then the genotype (Hor1) at the salinity level (6) decimals. It is noted that the gene expression values were irregular with the salt concentrations increased on the genotypes, and the results also showed that the genotypes under study showed gene expression with other salinity levels, but the expression value was lower compared to the salt concentrations (3, 9, and 6) decimals for some genotypes, as the

lowest value for gene expression was (0.466516) for the cultivar (Hor1) at a salt concentration of (9) decimals, while other genotypes had no gene expression in salt concentration, table 3.

The results of table 4, which represent the gene expression values of the GPX gene, indicate the presence of expression in some genotypes, as the cultivar (Koka1) recorded the highest gene expression at the salinity level (3) decimals, followed by the genotype (Hor1) at the salinity level (6), then the genotype (Afrod1) at the salt level (9) decimals, as it was noted that the gene expression values were uneven in the genotypes with the increase in salt concentrations, as the results showed that the structures under study showed gene expression with other of the salinity levels, and that the lowest value of gene expression was (0.101532) for cultivar (Hor1) at a salt concentration of (9) decimals.

the genotypes that gave genetic expression compared to other genotypes, this may be due to several reasons, including the genetic factors of the genotype and the extent of its adaptation to environmental conditions, as genes carry different in the amount of their gene expression in wheat varieties, especially in sensitive genotypes, so the detection of genes It is very important, in order to distinguish between genotypes and genotypes that are sensitive and tolerant to salinity, and that the difference in gene expression of genotypes grown under conditions of salt stress is an important genetic fingerprint of the cultivar, in order to distinguish it and compare it with the rest of the genotypes in the experiment (6) .

Figures 1, 2 and 3 show the accuracy and efficiency of the primers designed for the salt tolerance SOD and GPX genes, measure the amount of gene expression, and measure the melting point in compassion with housekeeping gene EF-alpha gene

Figure 1: Quantitative qPCR reaction for EF-alpha gene of five studied tomato cultivars

Figure 2: Quantitative qPCR reaction for GPX gene of five studied tomato cultivars

Figure 3: Quantitative qPCR reaction for SOD gene of five studied tomato cultivars

Conclusion:

The development and identification of tomato salinity tolerance genotypes are immediate requirements for defeat the challenge of tomato construction in arid regions that appearance complex limiting factors such as scarcity of freshwater, salinity, and heat stress. In this study, we evaluated five tomato of different groups. Our results accomplished that the impact of salt tension on tomato depends on the level of salt stress and genetic background inherited from the salt tolerance wild-type parent that provides the mechanisms of salt tolerance. Based on gene expression strategies in tomato plants which are SOD and GPX compared with reference

housekeeping gene, the results appear to have an interesting salt-tolerance mechanism during the preceding program of tomato plants.

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